

Protective Action of Rochelle Salt on Cupric Oxide Sol. Part I.

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The stabilising action of electrolytes on sols is well known, and instances of protection by ions of higher valency are also common where protection is preceded by a reversal of charge on the colloid. Friedemann and Neisser (*Munich Medical Weekly*, 1908, No. 11, 51) as well as Bechold (*Zeit. physikal. Chem.*, 1904, 48, 385) were the first to observe this reversal of charge on hydrophobe sols. Buxton and Teague (*Zeit. physikal. Chem.*, 1907, 57, 64, 76) in the case of platinum sols and ferric chloride, Krut and van der Speck (*Koll. Zeit.*, 1919, 25, 17) in the case of negative ferric oxide sol and disodium hydrogen phosphate, and Powis (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1915, 107, 818) also in the case of negative ferric oxide sol have studied this reversal of charge in a quantitative manner.

The following is an attempt to study the coagulation by an electrolyte of a sol the charge on which has already been reversed by another electrolyte. Thus cupric oxide sol prepared by Bredig's method was treated with varying concentrations of Rochelle salt, when reversal of charge was found to occur and the sol found to be rendered alkaline and more stable. If the concentration of the Rochelle salt in the mixture is well above 0.003 millimoles per litre the charge-reversal takes place without any previous coagulation.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The cupric oxide sol was prepared by the electrical dispersion method of Bredig. The electrodes were of pure electrolytic copper wires of 2 mm. thickness and six to seven inches in length. The make and break between them was secured by the use

of a light electric motor which kept one of the electrodes in constant vibration. (Paine, *Kolloidchem. Beihefte*, 1913, 4, 16.)

The spark-gap was about 1 mm. and a current of 8 amperes at 65 volts was used. Water redistilled in silica vessels and stored up in Jena glass vessels was used as the medium.

The light green sparks between the electrodes generated, after about fifteen minutes, a light green liquid, and as the sparking continued, the colour deepened till after an hour's sparking a brown liquid resulted. Thus every time a 500 c.c. Jena beakerful of sol was obtained, which, after settling, was stored in a large hard glass bottle for the following experiments. The amount of copper was determined iodometrically by means of thiosulphate and was found to be 0.0892 gm. of copper per litre.

The coagulation values of sodium sulphate for the pure sol as well as for the sol protected by different concentrations of Rochelle salt were found in the usual manner, keeping the volume constant in each case. The time allowed for the precipitation was three hours. A difference between the coagula of the unprotected and protected sols was noticeable: the coagulum of the protected sol consisted of particles much finer than those of the other.

The protected sol could also be reduced by glucose and hydrogen peroxide, etc., to an unstable cuprous oxide sol with a red-green fluorescence. Also, when the Rochelle salt was particularly dilute, e.g., 0.003 millimoles per litre, it no longer protected the sol but coagulated it.

Table I shows the relation between the concentration of Rochelle salt employed for protection and the corresponding coagulation values for sodium sulphate. These results could be repeated and a fair agreement obtained. Fig. 1 exhibits the relation between the concentration of Rochelle salt and the corresponding coagulation values for sodium sulphate and Fig. 2 illustrates the relation between the logarithms of the said quantities.

That the protection afforded was due to reversal of charge was verified by coagulating the protected sol with sodium sulphate and calcium sulphate. The coagulation values are given in Table II.

Another important fact observed was that when the concentration of Rochelle salt in the sol was greater than 800 millimoles per litre, the sol began to dissolve, there resulting in about 12 hours' time a blue-green solution.

TABLE I.

Rochelle salt in millimoles per litre.	Coagln. values for Na_2SO_4 in millimoles per litre.
nil	0.123
0.017	0.187
0.033	0.461
0.042	0.636
0.050	0.772
0.067	1.155
0.084	1.594
0.167	4.036
0.251	7.698
0.334	11.550
0.501	17.330
0.668	26.720
0.835	36.870
1.002	48.140
1.253	77.060

TABLE II.

Concn. of Rochelle salt (millimoles per litre)	Coagulation value of Na in millimoles per litre.	Coagulation value of Ca in millimoles per litre.
0.6667	58.34	1.76

Since Rochelle salt is optically active and the sol itself inactive, its adsorption by the latter was next investigated with the polarimeter. To 10 c.c. of sol a known volume of standard Rochelle salt was added and the total volume made up to 50 c.c. with distilled water. Rochelle salt solution as in above was next made up to 50 c.c. with distilled water alone. The rotations given by these were compared. By increasing the volumes of the standard Rochelle salt solution by stages eight sets of rotations with and without sol were

taken. The rotations were observed with a two-decimetre tube ; the source of illumination was an electric arc, the light from which was rendered monochromatic by a dichromate filter. As the arrangement was not very sensitive, sufficient reliance cannot be placed on these results.

The polarimetric readings were interpreted as follows. The rotation obtained with the sol to which Rochelle salt was added was assumed to be proportional to the equilibrium concentration, and the difference between this and the rotation given by pure Rochelle salt of the same concentration was taken as being proportional to the amount adsorbed.

The results obtained are tabulated below, the graphs showing the relation between the equilibrium rotation and the amount adsorbed, as also that between the logarithms of the two quantities are given in Figs. 3 and 4.

TABLE III.

Rotation of the equlm. concn. of Rochelle salt.	Rotn. cong. amt. adsorbed
0.22°	0.01°
0.34°	0.02°
0.53°	0.03°
0.68°	0.04°
0.81°	0.05°
1.05°	0.07°
1.16°	0.08°
1.35°	0.11°

In the above experiments care was taken not to let the concentration of the Rochelle salt overstep the limit where it dissolves the sol in course of time.

To make a closer study of this phenomenon of protection, experiments on absorption spectra were tried. On the addition of Rochelle salt to the sol, a slight change as regards transparency was observable—perhaps due to a change in the size of the particles—and this induced the attempt. The absorption spectra were photographed both in the ultraviolet as well as in the visible region.

Since on the addition of Rochelle salt to the sol no characteristic change was deducible from photography in the ultraviolet, attention

was turned to photography in the visible region. The constant-deviation spectrometer of Adam Hilger was used with Kodak's special rapid panchromatic films.

No perceptible distinction between the spectra of the sol with and without Rochelle salt was noticeable, both in the ultraviolet and the visible spectrographs.

Surface tension and viscosity measurements of the unprotected and protected sols were also made. But the results obtained did not characterise any difference ; so that no fresh light could be obtained from these experiments.

Conductivity measurements, however, go to show that the sol containing a known small concentration of Rochelle salt is more conducting than conductivity water containing the same concentration of the salt.

TABLE IV.

Conc. of Rochelle salt.	Conductivity in reciprocal ohms.	
	In water	In sol
8·75 mm. per litre.	0·0291	0·0298

That protection is preceded by a charge-reversal was conclusively established by cataphoretic experiments. The pure sol began to clear away from the anode in about 2 to 3 minutes and to rise in the cathode limb. On the other hand, the protected sol which contained 80 millimoles of Rochelle salt per litre took about fifteen minutes before it began to wander away from the cathode. Thus while the pure sol is positively charged, the protected sol carries a negative charge.

Discussion.

As a consequence of reversal of charge one should differentiate between two coagulation values, a lower one corresponding to the original sol and a higher one corresponding to the reversed sol. There is hardly any doubt that a reversed sol is quite a different sol from the original one, and for its coagulation, it is again the oppositely charged ions that are responsible according to their adsorbability and valency. Extensive work in this direction is lacking : but a few measurements of Friedemann and Neisser (*loc. cit.*) show it

distinctly. They showed that the coagulation values of mastix sol reversed by ferric chloride and aluminium sulphate are 60 millimoles and 1.7 millimoles per litre respectively. This corresponds to the big difference in coagulation values of chlorine ions and sulphate ions for positive sols.

Instead of taking the same electrolyte for reversal of charge and subsequent coagulation, different electrolytes were taken, *i.e.*, Rochelle salt and sodium sulphate. The stabilising action of Rochelle salt was shown to be limited, however, by two factors. In very small concentrations, it coagulates the sol; and in fairly large concentrations it dissolves the copper oxide and presents a slightly alkaline and light blue solution. In the intermediate concentrations, it has been shown that progressively increasing protection is afforded by larger and larger concentrations of Rochelle salt used; the coagulation values of the electrolyte sodium sulphate go on increasing with increasing concentrations of the protective agent between the limits (a) of coagulation at the first critical potential and (b) of solution by the latter.

It is well known that organic ions show generally greater adsorbability than simple inorganic ions. If the organic ion in question, besides being highly adsorbable, has a high valency a reversal of charge is what is to be expected. Such is the case with the tartrate ion with respect to copper oxide. It is evident from the data given (Table I, Figs. 1 and 2) that the adsorption of Rochelle salt by copper oxide sol increases with the concentration of the former. If it is assumed that at the coagulation point the charge on the protected sol is lowered to a minimum value, namely, the first critical potential of Powis, then this lowering is brought about, no doubt, by the adsorption of the alkali ion. If a further assumption is now made that owing to the very dilute nature of the sol and the dilute nature of the protective electrolyte contained in it, the amount of an ion adsorbed is small compared to the amount of electrolyte added, then Freundlich's isotherm may be written as

$$a = KC^{\frac{1}{2}}$$

where a is the amount adsorbed and C , the amount of electrolyte added. This, of course, is a first approximation. The tartrate adsorption may thus be expressed by

$$a_t = KC_t^{\frac{1}{2}}$$

where a_t is the amount of tartrate ion adsorbed against C_t the concentration added. Similarly

$$a_{Na} = K_1 C_{Na}^{\frac{1}{2}}$$

will express the relation between the amount of alkali ion adsorbed and the concentration of sodium sulphate added. Assuming then an equivalence in adsorption between the tartrate ion and the coagulating sodium ion, at the point of coagulation

$$KC_t^{\frac{1}{2}} = K_1 C_{Na}^{\frac{1}{2}}$$

so that if the coagulation values for sodium sulphate are plotted against the Rochelle salt concentration, Freundlich's adsorption isotherm ought to result. That it is so is borne out by Fig. 2. That the adsorption of tartrate follows Freundlich's isotherm is further shown by the results obtained from polarimetric measurements as given in Table III (Fig. 4). It is remarkable, however, that the curves (Figs. 1 and 3) bend towards the adsorption axis instead of the concentration axis as is generally the case, and yet Freundlich's adsorption isotherm is obeyed.

The lack of any definite results from absorption spectra both in the visible and ultraviolet regions may be partly due to the defect in the source of light, whose intensity could not be controlled and maintained constant, even for the short time of exposure, and partly to the very dilute nature of the sol which was subjected to these investigations. A characteristic difference in spectra was indeed once obtained which, however, could not be repeated.

It has been previously stated that Rochelle salt protects copper oxide sol between certain limits. At the lower one coagulation occurs and at the higher solution takes place. The process of solution near about this higher limit is a slow one and no sudden change is brought to light. It follows clearly from this that adsorption is merely the first stage in chemical action. When the tartrate ions are preferentially adsorbed by the copper oxide particles, hydroxyl ions make their appearance in solution, and when these reach a certain concentration, probably a readjustment in the forces of valency occurs, and a new compound is formed. The nature of this new compound has been the subject of study of the next part. It appears also that the presence of hydroxyl ions is

necessary for the formation of the new blue compound, and a limiting value for such concentration can be laid down.

One is indeed tempted to ascribe the protective action to the formation of a second colloid within the first. During the process of sparking, copper oxide particles, some copper ions and hydroxyl ions are formed. Of these, the copper oxide particles adsorb the less mobile copper ions, thus forming a positively charged sol, with a surrounding second layer of hydroxyl ions. When Rochelle salt is added the tartrate ion is adsorbed in excess forming negatively charged colloidal copper tartrate and displacing the hydroxyl ions. These in turn react with the copper tartrate forming a soluble basic tartrate; thus results the blue liquid for the higher limit of the Rochelle salt concentration.

Summary.

(1) The protective action of Rochelle salt on copper oxide sol was studied; a relation between the protecting power and the concentration of protective agent was obtained on the basis of the coagulation values of the protected sol. Thus the coagulation values for sodium sulphate were found to increase with the concentration of Rochelle salt employed as a protective agent. When the logarithms of the coagulation values are plotted against the logarithms of concentrations of Rochelle salt used, a straight line was obtained.

(2) The adsorption of Rochelle salt by the sol was further studied with the polarimeter and Freundlich's relation was found to hold.

(3) The curves obtained showing the relation between concentration and adsorption were found to be bent away from the concentration axis, unlike the ordinary isotherms.

(4) A comparison of the absorption spectra of the protected and the pure sol was made by taking photographs both in the visible and ultraviolet regions.

(5) Cataphoretic experiments showed that the protection by Rochelle salt was due to a reversal of charge.

(6) A mechanism of protection and coagulation has been suggested.

FIG. 1.

FIG. II.

FIG. III.

FIG. IV.